

Deliverable 5.5

Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Final version

White Research
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R **BIN**

**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

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the European Union

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ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
CCRI-CSO	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office
D&C	Dissemination and Communication Strategy
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MARC	Multi-Actor Regional Constellations
PO	Project Officer
SMA s	Social Media Accounts
SRA	Southern Regional Assembly

This project has used a standard methodology already developed in INCENTIVE project (Grant Agreement number: 101005330), and RRI2SCCALE (Grand Agreement number: 872526), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for ROBIN (Grant Agreement number: 101060504)

Executive summary

This report represents the final version of the **Deliverable 5.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) – Initial version**, as well as the **Deliverable 5.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results - Interim Version (M18)** of the Horizon Europe ROBIN project (GA 101060504). This document is the **Deliverable 5.5 Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Final version** and outlines detailed insights on all aspects of ROBIN's communication and dissemination strategy up to August 2025 (Month 36). Furthermore, it provides all the communication and dissemination tools and channels that have been used throughout the lifespan of the ROBIN project, aiming to enhance its visibility and maximise its reach in terms of dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The chapters of this document represent the most updated versions of both the Initial version of the DCP, submitted in November 2022 (M3), and the Interim version, submitted in February 2024 (M18). They are organised as follows:

- Chapter 1: An introduction to the DCP and its goals;
- Chapter 2: A brief description of the ROBIN project;
- Chapter 3: An overview of the dissemination, communication activities, along with the target audiences, messages, and channels;
- Chapter 4: An overview of the monitoring and evaluation of processes, including the key metrics used to measure the impact of communication and dissemination activities;
- Chapter 5: A brief analysis of dissemination and communication impact, covering the channels and activities used, along with key metrics from social media, the project website, newsletters, events (both project-related and external), and established synergies;
- Chapter 6: The conclusions of the final DCP.

The Annexes include:

- ➔ The dissemination and communication reporting template: This is the template that all partners needed to update on a monthly basis with information about all the dissemination and communication activities.

Following the successful approach implemented during the initial months of the project, ROBIN placed a lot of emphasis on increasing visibility and reach through strategic actions aimed at promoting the project's results and findings. **The active involvement of all consortium partners in dissemination and communication efforts significantly expanded stakeholder outreach, reaching 204,929 individuals.** As in previous period, the available metrics indicate that the most effective communication and dissemination channels were: (i) the continuous participation of project partners in numerous scientific conferences and high-attendance external events, (ii) the organisation of ROBIN's regional workshops across the five pilot regions, as well as (iii) the ongoing promotion of the project's support actions and findings through its social media platforms and website.

1. Introduction

It is crucial to disseminate and communicate the project's vision and results in an effective way to ensure the successful implementation of the ROBIN project. This deliverable presents the final version of the DCP, outlines the operational framework for its implementation, and summarises the outcomes of the dissemination and communication strategy throughout the lifespan of the ROBIN project.

The main objective of ROBIN's Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy was to define the actions carried out and the tools were used for the promotion of the project's results. On top of that, the strategy presented in D5.1 provided a specific plan to raise awareness around the project and support ROBIN's implementation, which was further enriched in D5.3, the Interim version of the DCP. Thus, besides supporting the exploitation of ROBIN outcomes, the DCP ensured the sustainability of the assets developed during the project's lifecycle.

In particular, the DCP offered the answers to some fundamental questions about the communication and dissemination activities of the project:

Table 1. Summary of D&C's key questions

Key questions	ROBIN's DCP
What?	Key messages
To Whom?	Target audiences
Who?	Roles & Responsibilities
How?	Communication tools and channels, guidelines, and templates
When?	Timeline

As stated in both D5.1 and D5.3, the guidelines, templates, and annexes produced in the report are subject to updates in line with the project's progress. Throughout the entire duration of the ROBIN project (M1-M36), a series of targeted dissemination and communication activities was carried out to enhance visibility and understanding of the project's goals. These efforts were played a key role in raising awareness as well as in reaching regional target audiences, effectively complementing related activities at the EU level. **The DCP was designed as a strategic roadmap, providing consortium partners with clear guidance to effectively plan and execute communication and engagement activities.**

All partners reported their main dissemination and communication activities on an ad-hoc basis, submitting updates each time an activity occurred by filling out the dissemination activities reporting Excel file. At the end of each month, WR sent reminders to all partners to ensure timely and complete reporting, enabling a comprehensive overview and effective monitoring of all actions. The dissemination activities included organising or participating in events or conferences, training

sessions, pitch events, joint activities with other Horizon Europe projects, communication campaigns (e.g., radio, TV), non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publications, press releases, and more. This report presents the evaluation results based on the data collected through this internal monitoring and reporting process.

2. About ROBIN project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfill this role with support to co-shape their governance structures to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. The ROBIN project demonstrated the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia, and Greece. ROBIN's team set up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). The multidisciplinary consortium of ROBIN provided the regions with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process, ROBIN coordinates its actions with the CCRI-CSO.

The ambition of the EU-funded, ROBIN project was to accelerate the deployment of circular bioeconomy at the regional level in 5 European pilot regions. The project's goal was to support the adaptation of governance models through multi-stakeholder engagement and coordination and promote social innovation.

Thus, the overall objectives of the ROBIN project were:

- ✓ Deeper understanding of existing bioeconomy governance practices and models in Europe
- ✓ Enhanced understanding of the bioeconomy's benefits amongst all stakeholders (including primary biomass producers as well as consumers)
- ✓ Improved regional governance models with increased stakeholder engagement accelerating the circular bioeconomy transition of European regions
- ✓ Better informed bioeconomy strategies creating conducive conditions for investments in sustainable business opportunities offered by local bio-based economies
- ✓ Improved environmental footprint of bio-based products and services
- ✓ Increased cross-regional coordination under the CCRI reinforcing the EU science-policy interface for addressing Sustainable Development Goals

During the lifespan of ROBIN project, the multidisciplinary consortium of ROBIN has organised several events and workshops to inform the audience about important findings and updates on the progress of the project.

Lastly, the dimension of sustainability was pivotal to the goals of the project. As such, the dissemination and communication efforts were vital for the maximisation of its impact and value extraction. Creating multiple channels for taking advantage of the project assets was a key priority for ROBIN and it became apparent that dissemination and communication activities were significant, as they leveraged the sustainability of the project's positive impacts.

3. ROBIN Dissemination and communication activities

Throughout the ROBIN project's lifespan, a set of dissemination and communication activities have been carried out to promote its goals, messages, toolbox, and results to a wide range of stakeholders across Europe and beyond, while also enhancing the project's visibility. These activities were implemented in line with the initial Dissemination and Communication Plan, developed in November 2022 (M3), to assist and support consortium partners in their communication efforts. The plan aimed to ensure the efficient and effective dissemination of the project's findings. Furthermore, an enhanced Dissemination and Communication Plan was developed in February 2024 (M18), incorporating updates based on preliminary findings on the effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities carried out during the first half of the project.

Overall, the ROBIN dissemination strategy outlined a set of overarching, practical objectives which were further expanded in the updated Dissemination and Communication Plan (M18) to address emerging needs during the project's duration. These objectives are briefly presented below:

- Present the project's aim, vision, activities, and events to a wider audience;
- Promote awareness raising among stakeholder groups;
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities;
- Engage stakeholders through a series of relevant activities, events, and conferences;
- Ensure that the key messages are communicated to its target audiences;
- Ensure the exploitation of the project's outcomes;
- Plan, organise, monitor, and fine-tune the project's dissemination activities and events;
- Establish and sustain synergies with other relevant national and European projects and networks;
- Disseminate the project's lessons learned and outcomes in an open and transparent way;
- Support the visibility and engagement activities of ROBIN's pilot regions;
- Store all project's key outcomes and results on ROBIN's website;
- Disseminate key outcomes and results through ROBIN's SMAs;
- Promote open access to ROBIN's deliverables and data.

3.1 Promoting ROBIN

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) of ROBIN focused on promoting the project's core messages and key results to its target audiences.

Given the varied and different background of stakeholders, messages were customised to suit the unique needs of each group. These messages either promoted project results or encouraged active involvement, such as invitations to events or requests for feedback and validation.

Table 2 lists the targeted stakeholder groups along with their needs and tailored messages. These final key messages were defined throughout the project's lifecycle based on the actual ROBIN data and outcomes, align closely with those outlined in the original D&C Plan, demonstrating their continued relevance, and strong alignment with the needs of the target groups.

Table 2. ROBIN target audience, needs and messages

Target Group	Needs	Messages
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Policy actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Understand the current landscape of regional bioeconomy governance models – Explore new ways of establishing regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy – Better informed and effective policies for developing regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy – Explore new ways of engaging stakeholders from different backgrounds – Develop new regional strategies – Integrate social innovation into the policy development process – More examples of applied best practices and how to replicate them – Enhance the knowledge of how to coordinate CCRI actions with EU-funded projects – Achieve progress toward meeting regional, national, and EU policy targets – Introduce a more socio-economic and environmental approach to the development of regional governance models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increased policy recommendations on how to create regional bioeconomy models ✓ Enhanced engagement of stakeholders in bioeconomy models ✓ Improved, more inclusive, and better-informed governance models based on stakeholder engagement ✓ Further insights on local potentialities along with the means to tap into them for stimulating bio-based and social innovation ✓ Increased support to raise awareness amongst regional bioeconomy stakeholders and engage them in building and improving governance models
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Bioeconomy industry & actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increase the market penetration of biobased innovations – Develop bio-based value chains that deliver sustainable products/ services – Capitalise on emerging investment opportunities in bio-based sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increased networking and stakeholder engagement opportunities to build connections required to accelerate bio-based innovation ✓ Enhanced integration of bio-based value chain development into broader policies and regional development plans ✓ Increased awareness of bioeconomy and its benefits ✓ Increased demand for bio-based products/services

Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Advance research in focal scientific fields related to bioeconomy – Keep in line with industry and policy developments in the bioeconomy field – Follow recent developments and research trends – Identify research gaps for further research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Aggregation and classification of existing scientific knowledge of types of bioeconomy governance models ✓ New knowledge and empirical open data on the application of novel inclusive governance models
Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increased socioeconomic and environmental benefits from established policies – Plethora of more sustainable, healthier, and affordable products and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ A more meaningful engagement in regional bioeconomy governance and policy making ✓ Increased understanding of the bioeconomy and how to make better-informed and more sustainable choices.
Relevant EU projects, CCRI & other EU initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Exchange knowledge with other experts in the field – Share their results and promote their concept to other initiatives and the general public – Establish synergies and expand their network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Deliverables with the project results to enhance further research in the field ✓ A network of synergies that facilitates collaboration and knowledge transfer between relevant initiatives ✓ Increased support in the dissemination of the project's results
Organisations & Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Stay updated regarding the latest developments in the bioeconomy and policy development field – Engage and inform more citizens about social innovative governance structures on bioeconomy – Stay informed about the progress regarding the establishment of regional bioeconomy models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Ways to integrate best practices derived from the project into the development of regional bioeconomy models

3.2 Target audiences

The ROBIN project followed a well-structured and targeted communication and dissemination strategy. Messages and communication actions were adapted based on the type of stakeholders, the benefits they could gain from the project, and the potential impact on each group.

The dissemination and communication strategy has primarily supported the consortium's efforts to engage its main target groups, based on the Quadruple Helix model and also expanded to include additional stakeholder categories relevant to the project's scope and objectives, as outlined below:

1. Policy actors (Directorate Generals of the European Commission, EU policymakers, National governments, Local governments, Regional authorities, Policy advisors)
2. Civil society (consumers, clusters & action groups)

3. Researchers & academia
4. Horizon projects, CCRI projects & other EU initiatives
5. Regional bioeconomy actors (e.g., primary biomass producers)
6. Bio-based SMEs & Industries (e.g., biobased industrial companies)
7. Innovation & policy advisors
8. Financial Institutions
9. Bioeconomy Experts
10. General public
11. International Organisations

Table 3. ROBIN target audience categories

Target Group	Short description	Sub-categories
Policy actors	Decision-makers at European, national, and regional levels that are expected to play a key role in policy design.	Directorate Generals of the European Commission EU policymakers National governments Local governments Regional authorities Policy advisors
Bioeconomy industry & actors	All actors that are active in the field of bioeconomy and regional development.	Biobased SMEs Bioeconomy experts Biobased industrial companies Innovation Advisors Investors Regional bioeconomy actors Primary biomass producers
Scientific community	Network of interacting scientists who conduct research in the fields of bioeconomy, regional development, and biobased products	Research Centres Research groups Individual researchers Universities
Civil Society	Individuals who are interested in enhancing their knowledge of bioeconomy, biobased products	General public Consumers Clusters Action Groups

<p>Relevant EU projects, CCRI & other EU initiatives</p>	<p>Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects as well as other European and national projects and initiatives</p>	<p>CCRI H2020 projects Horizon Europe projects Other EU-funded projects (e.g., Interreg, Erasmus+)</p>
<p>Organisations & Institutions</p>	<p>Organisations (governmental and non-governmental) and Institutions that are active in the bioeconomy field</p>	<p>International Organisations NGOs Financial Institutions Governmental Institutions</p>

3.3 Dissemination and communication channels and activities

ROBIN utilised a combination of online and offline communication and dissemination channels and activities to enhance the project’s visibility among diverse stakeholder groups. Over the course of the project, these efforts included:

- ROBIN’s logo and visual identity;
- ROBIN’s promotional materials including leaflet, poster, templates, and letterhead;
- ROBIN’s Social Media Accounts (SMAs) including Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube, and X;
- ROBIN’s website;
- ROBIN’s newsletters and promotional video;
- Project and external events;
- Public deliverables and academic publications;
- Synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives;
- ROBIN’s Train-the-Trainer Workshop;
- ROBIN’s Joint Final Conference.

Figure 1. ROBIN's dissemination and communication activities

Throughout the project's lifespan, these D&C channels and activities were adopted and systematically structured into four key stages.

❖ **First phase – Early in the project (M1-M6):**

During the first phase of the project, the D&C strategy was designed. In the framework of the D&C strategy, several key aspects were identified such as the targeted stakeholder groups that will be reached during the project, as well as the messages that will be used to engage them. In addition, the selection of suitable metrics for monitoring the successful implementation of the strategy took place, and the consortium partners' responsibilities were clearly defined. Besides developing the D&C strategy, the first months of the project were dedicated to the production of the dissemination material, as well as the establishment of the dissemination and communication tools. The project's visual identity and logo, the promotional material (leaflet, poster, templates, letterhead), the SMAs, and the project's website was developed in the first 4 months of the project. Finally, the first dissemination of the project to the broader public took place through contacts with other projects, press releases, our newsletters, the continuous posting on our SMAs and by participating in external events.

❖ **Second phase – During the project (M7 - M25):**

Throughout the project, constant interaction between the project partners and the relevant stakeholders has been established. An active community interested in the ROBIN project has been created and maintained through the SMAs. In addition, synergies are developed with other projects and initiatives relevant to the topics of bioeconomy, sustainability and circular economy, and regional development. Multiple activities have already taken place and were planned to take place within the second phase of the project including dissemination events, workshops, webinars, meetings with the CCRI-CSO, mutual learning workshops, joint events, and dissemination activities with the sister projects. Publications and promotion of the project's results through the website and the bi-annual Newsletter has further maximised the project's impact. Finally, the participation of consortium partners in external events and conferences, as well as their connections to key networks from the sector was leveraged in order to promote the project to a wider audience.

❖ **Third phase – End of the project (M26 - M36):**

Although the dissemination of the project's vision continued, this phase of the project mainly focused on the dissemination of the project's results and outcomes. In particular, toward the end of the lessons learned permitted consortium partners to draft some key recommendations that can support the adoption of sustainability certification schemes. The project's community will be further engaged to ensure its continuation after the project's completion. Furthermore, a joint final event has been organised in collaboration with other five Horizon Europe projects aiming to present the project's results, diffuse the knowledge and engage relevant stakeholders in the post-project exploitation of the findings.

❖ **Fourth phase – Beyond the end of the project:**

The ambition of ROBIN'S consortium is to continue promoting the project's vision and results even after the official end of the project ensuring that the project's outcomes will reach as many relevant stakeholders as possible. Relevant publications will further disseminate the project's legacy even after the official completion.

4. Monitoring and evaluation of activities

4.1 Assessment of metrics

The monitoring mechanisms were crucial to secure the successful implementation of the D&C strategy and ensure the achievement of the DCP goals: in essence, they measured the impact of the dissemination efforts. Therefore, a monitoring process has been set up at the beginning of the project. This process supported us to identify any potential gaps and problems, the special needs of relevant stakeholders, and good practices that we can adopt. In this way, we aimed to ensure the effective dissemination of the outcomes to the project's key stakeholders and the general public.

White Research was responsible for monitoring all communication and dissemination activities within the ROBIN project. Additionally, the WR team supported partners in completing the dissemination reporting Excel file and sent monthly reminders to ensure all actions were properly documented.

A set of KPIs was monitored to evaluate the impact of the DCP activities. The dissemination manager, with the support of the consortium partners, has monitored the quantitative metrics throughout the reporting periods.

Below is presented the list of KPIs for the dissemination and communication activities of ROBIN in M36:

Table 4. Key Performance Indicators

Assessed element	Metric	Target (M36)	Current Status (M36)
<i>Unique visits to the project website</i>	Nr. of visits (total)	> 10,000	14,000
<i>Social media accounts (Linked In, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter)</i>	Nr. of followers	> 1,000	1,550
<i>Newsletter</i>	Nr. of published Newsletters	6	6
<i>Project workshops and events</i>	Nr. of workshops	≥ 22	29
<i>Participation in external events/ conferences</i>	Nr. of events	≥ 15	58
<i>Views of the promotional video</i>	Nr. of views (total)	> 500	642
<i>Synergies with initiatives & networks</i>	Nr. of joint actions	15	31
<i>Scientific publications</i>	Nr. of scientific publications	3	4
<i>Promotional material distributed</i>	Nr. of promotional material distributed	>300	1,430
<i>Stakeholders engaged in overall</i>	Nr. of stakeholders engaged	3,000	>204,929

ROBIN not only achieved its KPIs but also exceeded them, thanks to the active involvement and consistent participation of consortium partners throughout the project's duration. Their contributions ranging from attending various external events to promoting ROBIN through social media channels and their respective websites, played a key role in this success.

The KPI related to the distribution of promotional material is based on an indicative number that accounts for the use of various materials, including the logo, presentations, roll-up banners, and leaflets. At numerous high-attendance events (e.g., conferences with 5,000 to 10,000 participants), ROBIN leaflets were distributed. However, due to the unavailability of precise distribution numbers at these large-scale events, they were not included in the final count. Conversely, at smaller events with lower attendance (e.g., 30 to 50 participants), where the exact number of leaflets distributed was also not recorded, we used the total number of participants as a reference for estimating outreach.

4.2. Dissemination reporting by partners

Throughout the duration of the project, all consortium partners reported their dissemination and communication activities on an ad-hoc basis by filling in the template shared by WR (online in the project's repository) each time they perform a dissemination activity. Each semester (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36) WR consolidated the results and developed the semestrial technical reporting of WP6.

For keeping track of the activities performed by the consortium partners, a reporting template has been designed and shared (Annex).

Table 5. Annex for Dissemination

Annex	Dissemination Tool	Coverage	When
Annex I	Dissemination reporting template	All dissemination activities carried out by the partners every month.	Ad-hoc basis throughout the project

Dissemination reporting template: This template recorded all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The document has been updated by all partners on an ad-hoc basis. Keeping track of the activities ensured that any problems or gaps will be observed early, and mitigation measures will be put in place in order to be solved. Partners were requested to fill out the form **within 5 days** for any dissemination and communication activity they are involved in. Also, partners were encouraged to inform WR when an event is scheduled and share some brief information (e.g., event, location, dates) as well as take photos & keep the agenda.

Each project partner immediately contacted WR, should any risks be identified concerning communication and dissemination activities, or in case problems arise during the implementation of publicity actions.

5. Dissemination and communication results: channels and activities

5.1 Promotional material and identity

The project's promotional materials were primarily used at both virtual and in-person project events, external events and conferences attended by consortium partners, and in day-to-day publicity efforts. They were also featured at the Joint Final Conference and the Train-the-Trainer workshop. The promotional materials included:

- ➔ Project logo and visual identity;
- ➔ Leaflet and poster;
- ➔ Templates for publications, presentations, and reports;
- ➔ Letterhead;
- ➔ Ad-hoc promotional material (tailored to the project's activities and needs);
- ➔ Newsletters;

The ROBIN leaflet, in particular, served as a key promotional material in the project's dissemination and communication activities. Over the three-year duration, the ROBIN visual identity was consistently applied across all promotional channels to ensure a coherent and recognisable presence throughout all communication efforts.

Figure 2. ROBIN Project logo

Figure 3. The front and back side of the ROBIN leaflet

Figure 4. ROBIN .ppt presentation template

Figure 5. Printed copies of ROBIN Leaflet

Figure 6. ROBIN Poster presented at external events

In addition to the standard promotional package, and with the aim of increasing the project's visibility while supporting consortium partners in their communication efforts, White Research developed additional materials including factsheets, to promote the support actions in the pilot regions. All promotional items adhered to the project's visual identity to ensure consistency.

Figure 7. Ad-hoc promotional material - Factsheet

5.2 Promotional video

The promotional video of the project was produced in M9. The video presented briefly and in an animated way the project, its objectives, and future outcomes.

The video creation process is described as follows. First, a video script was prepared, which included the video's sequence and key phrases explaining the project's objectives, ROBIN's aims, and approach. All partners provided valuable feedback to enhance the script. After incorporating partners' comments and suggestions, the initial storyboard was ready. By providing feedback and suggestions for improvement once more, the storyboard was finalised, and the animated final version was completed.

The video aimed to reach a broad audience through social networks. It has been uploaded to the project's YouTube channel [here](#), the project's website [here](#), and shared on all ROBIN's SMAs. The purpose of the promotional video was to introduce the viewer to the project in an understandable and engaging manner. Many terms and concepts used in the project, such as 'Quadruple Helix Stakeholders,' 'governance models,' 'bioeconomy practices,' etc., were not widely known, so it was crucial to communicate them at the EU level in a simple and accessible manner, encouraging viewers to engage with the project.

In terms of content, the video followed a narrative approach, featuring elements that described ROBIN's objectives and assets. The diversity of characters reflected the project's inclusive vision. This approach was designed to be welcoming and inclusive, making the project accessible to a broad

audience, regardless of their familiarity with bioeconomy and regional governance models. Subtitles have been added in all ROBIN's pilot regions languages; Greek, Spanish, Slovakian, and German to cater to the audiences of all pilot regions. The video's duration was limited to 2 minutes and 20 seconds to maintain the viewer's attention. Finally, to enhance accessibility for an international audience, the amount of written text has been kept to a minimum, considering that not all viewers may be fluent in English. The following figures present some screenshots of ROBIN's promotional video.

Figure 8. ROBIN's promotional video screenshots from YouTube channel (left) and website (right)

ROBIN's promotional video on its YouTube channel **has reached over 642 views, surpassing the KPI target of 500 views**. Additionally, the video was actively promoted through ROBIN's social media channels, with consortium partners further enhancing its reach by sharing it within their respective social media platforms.

5.3 ROBIN Website

The ROBIN website served as a key tool for enhancing project visibility. As outlined in the initial Dissemination and Communication Plan (D5.1), a draft website structure was developed to serve as the baseline and has been updated as needed to align with the project's evolving requirements and progress.

The website became operational in M5 (January 2023) and has since served as the online platform for disseminating news and updates. The website's structure and content have been designed for user-friendliness and to clearly convey the project's concept, pilot universities, and objectives. Additionally, the website contained key information about the project's progress, including news and event announcements, to keep stakeholders informed. Rather than targeting a specific audience, the website worked as a dynamic repository of project information and news, making it an online platform for reaching out to a broad range of stakeholders. WR was the partner responsible for the website's development, maintenance, and technical management, as well as overseeing web editing and content development. The website's URL is <https://robin-project.eu/>, and the project's contact email aligns with it (info@robin-project.eu).

Although WR, as the dissemination manager, was the main responsible for the website management and content, all partners contributed to the content development with news and other dissemination material. The website was active throughout the duration of the project and included regular updates on the project's progress, internal and external events, relevant projects and initiatives, reports and project results, as well as other news from the bioeconomy field.

The website was developed using WordPress. Special attention was given to creating a responsive and accessible website, ensuring compatibility with various devices, including mobile ones, to prevent the exclusion of potential stakeholders. The website included some general information about the project and dedicated sections to present the team members and the members of the Advisory Board, all project outcomes such as public reports, dissemination material, and newsletters (also available for downloading) and a dedicated section for the pilot regions as the territorial approach and Multi-Actor Regional Constellations were a key asset of the project. In addition, the website featured in the regional profiles sections, the regional vision and bioeconomy profile in both English and national languages. It also included a dedicated section which redirects the user to the ROBIN's Toolbox. The project's Privacy and Cookies Policy is available on the website. More specifically, some screenshots from the website are presented below:

Figure 9. ROBIN's website homepage

Figure 10. About ROBIN website section

Figure 11. ROBIN's pilot regions website section

Figure 12. ROBIN's 1st Newsletter

Figure 13. ROBIN's 2nd Newsletter

For monitoring the website's traffic, we utilised the Google Analytics platform. Since the project's Toolbox is integrated into the website, Google Analytics is also used to monitor the Toolbox's traffic analytics which will be included into the KPI "unique visit's to project's website". This tool provided valuable statistics that assist us in optimising the website and our dissemination strategy.

Figure 14. ROBIN's website engagement overview

Figure 15. ROBIN users by country

The team successfully maintained an active digital presence for ROBIN project by consistently promoting consortium activities and events through its website and social media channels. Implementing a strategic schedule by posting at least twice per week, they shared articles highlighting partners' participation in external events and webinars, as well as updates on project workshops. This regular dissemination of content has significantly contributed to increased traffic on the ROBIN website.

All consortium partners actively engaged in dissemination and communication activities, enhancing the project's visibility by consistently sharing content related to ROBIN's actions and events on their social media platforms. They also contributed by reposting content from ROBIN's official channels and publishing articles on their respective websites. **These coordinated efforts enabled our team to reach the final website KPI, with more than 14,000 Unique visitors.**

5.4 Social Media Accounts

ROBIN's SMAs have proven to be valuable tools for consistently promoting the project and its ongoing activities in a visually engaging and interactive manner. ROBIN's Facebook page, Twitter account, LinkedIn profile, and YouTube channel have been established in October 2022 (M2). Given the widespread daily use by our targeted stakeholders, SMAs have been leveraged to the fullest extent, making them essential digital communication channels for the project's efforts to establish and expand its stakeholder base. Furthermore, SMAs facilitated the redirection of the audience to the ROBIN's website, often by promoting existing content from the website, thus playing an integral role in our communication strategy. Table 6 below presents some key metrics from the project's social media channels, including the total number of followers and posts.

Table 6. ROBIN Social Media Accounts metrics

Social Media Platform	Metric	M36
Facebook	No of Followers	119
	No of Posts	190
	Total Impressions	3,654
Twitter / X	No of Followers	484
	No of Posts	269
LinkedIn	No of Followers	913
	No of Posts	194
	Total Impressions	> 50,000
YouTube	No of Subscribers	34
	No of Video Views	642

Overall, the **use of Facebook** has also been beneficial for sharing news with followers. Since the launch of Facebook (October 2022) and by August 2025, **190 posts have been uploaded to ROBIN's page**. We believe that our social media strategy has proven to be successful, **achieving 119 followers** as of August 2025, and enabling ROBIN to communicate effectively within the Facebook community. The effectiveness of the account is evident when considering the Facebook metric Total reach (3.654 views) which shows the number of people who have seen any Facebook posts within their news feeds, on the ROBIN page, and as shared by their networks. This metric also includes people who do not follow ROBIN on Facebook. To monitor the performance of the ROBIN page, Facebook Analytics tool is used.

Figure 16. ROBIN's Facebook page analytics

Due to some limitations in accessing **Twitter / X Analytics**, and specifically, the requirement to pay for account performance metrics, we decided to discontinue publishing on our Twitter account as of January 2025. This decision was made collectively by all partners during a scheduled monthly meeting, following a discussion on the platform's cost-effectiveness and its alignment with our communication strategy. Despite discontinuing activity on the platform, we successfully **reached 484 followers and published a total of 269 posts**.

LinkedIn Analytics has limitations in terms of data retention and accessibility. Taking this into consideration, and focusing on the period from January 2023 to August 2025, we estimate that **the total number of impressions is indicative of exceeding 50,000**. This important metric indicates that ROBIN's content successfully captured audience interest, demonstrating the broad reach and visibility of our messaging across the target audience.

Figure 17. LinkedIn Posts Impressions (Jan '23 - Jan '24)

Figure 18. LinkedIn Posts Impressions (Aug '24 - Aug '25)

Throughout the entire duration of the project, **LinkedIn served as the primary platform for communication and dissemination activities.** As of August 2025, the ROBIN LinkedIn page **successfully reached and engaged 913 followers.** Through the use of LinkedIn, ROBIN had the opportunity to stay engaged with Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) developments and participate in professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest within a wide range of professional networks.

LinkedIn also played a key role in promoting ROBIN’s final event to a broader audience. A targeted campaign was launched in the context of the final event, featuring dedicated posts that introduced speakers of each panel session. **This approach significantly increased visibility and interest. Furthermore, the post published on the day of the final event (Figure 17) emerged as one of the most engaging posts, generating 743 impressions and 363 clicks.** These metrics reflect a strong level of anticipation and interest from the audience in the project’s outcomes.

Figure 19. ROBIN's Most Engaging Post (Jun '24 - Jun '25)

The video post summarising key insights from the final event featuring highlights such as participant attendance and the signing of the Memorandum of Collaboration (MoC) among ROBIN’s regional partners, proved to be also one of the most engaging posts on LinkedIn. Specifically, the post received significant attention, achieving **245 video views**, **523 impressions**, and **over than 40 reactions**, reflecting strong interest and positive engagement from the business and research community.

Figure 20. ROBIN's one of the most engaging posts (Jun '24 - Jun '25)

ROBIN’s YouTube Channel has 34 subscribers, with the promotional video has more than 642 views in total.

ROBIN’s social media followers in total have reached 1,550, surpassing the KPI target of 1,000. Specifically, the audience is distributed across platforms as follows: **913 followers on LinkedIn, 119 on Facebook, 484 on Twitter / X, and 34 subscribers on YouTube.**

5.5 The ROBIN Newsletters

ROBIN has committed to producing a bi-annual newsletter on a semi-annual basis. Six newsletters have been distributed to the project’s target audience and uploaded to the project’s website. Each newsletter summarises the updates on the project’s progress and actions, providing an alternative way to inform existing subscribers about the project’s results. Furthermore, the newsletter served as a means to attract and retain stakeholders who are not familiar with social media, as well as citizens who may not have been sufficiently interested during the initial phases of the project.

The newsletters were prepared by WR, with partners contributing specific content when necessary. The Mailchimp platform has been used for the development and distribution of the newsletter, as well as for capturing analytics. The newsletter included the following sections: (i) an introductory section, (ii) project updates, (iii) information about upcoming events, (iv) details about sister projects, and (v) any other special sections.

Regarding the subscription to the newsletter, all GDPR provisions will be adhered to. Subscribers were required to agree to the project's Privacy Policy, and they had the option to unsubscribe from the newsletter at any time.

A dedicated website section at the bottom of the website featuring the ROBIN newsletter subscription has been included to facilitate new subscribers. ROBIN's newsletter managed to reach **127 subscribers**.

The form is titled "STAY IN TOUCH" and includes the following fields: "First name*", "Last name*", "info@company.com*", "Company", "Country*", and "Position". There is a checkbox for "I give ROBIN PROJECT the consent to collect and process my data according to the Privacy and Cookies Policy*". A green button at the bottom says "Sign me up for the newsletter!".

Figure 21. ROBIN newsletter subscription

Figure 22. ROBIN 1st and 5th Newsletter

The Newsletter was sent to all the subscribers upon its release and each issue was also uploaded on the project’s website. Overall, the ROBIN newsletter has proven to be an effective channel for reaching virtual followers.

5.6 ROBIN’s Events

The events organised in the framework of ROBIN aim to raise awareness around the concept of the project, promote the project’s results and facilitate the engagement of key stakeholders which will support the project’s activities and provide feedback on the produced outcomes. Several events, such as stakeholder engagement events, mutual learning workshops, and a final dissemination event promoted the exploitation of ROBIN’s results.

Throughout the entire ROBIN duration, a series of events was organised to:

- (i) align ROBIN’S support actions to regional needs (co-creation workshops);
- (ii) design tailored action plans (action plan workshop);
- (iii) catalyse connections and enhance understanding of bioeconomy amongst regional stakeholders (stakeholder engagement events);
- (iv) exchange knowledge across regions (mutual learning workshops);
- (v) build capacity amongst stakeholders around Europe (train-the-trainers event); and
- (vi) disseminate final results (final event in M36).

The following types of events are scheduled as part of the project’s plan:

Table 7. ROBIN events

Event	WP, Task, responsible partner	Short description	Date (estimation)	Status
5 regional co-creation events (one in each region) comprised of 2 sessions	WP2, T2.1, CTA, support: all	<p>Session 1: Validation and prioritisation of key barriers, potentialities, and opportunities to be pursued;</p> <p>Session 2: Definition of improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s) (including novel business models and social measures)</p>	M1-M15	✓ Done

Action Plan Workshop	WP2, T2.2, CTA, support: all	A workshop where the regional partners will shape Action Plans detailing the specific support actions that will be offered in their region. The concrete output of this task is an Action Plan for each ROBIN region (D2.2)	M10-M16	✓ Done
Regional partners will run 2 stakeholder engagement events (2 per region)	WP3, T3.2, BPRO, support: all	Events to engage stakeholders in the frame of the support actions where feedback will be collected from major testing	M18-M30	✓ Done
Digital validation workshop	WP3, T3.3, S2I, support: all	Validation workshop of the Toolbox with the Advisory Board	M16-M32	✓ Done
2 mutual learning workshops and missions (DE and SK)	WP4, T4.2, CTA, support: all	In collaboration with the respective regional partners to exchange information	M18-M34	✓ Done
Train-the-Trainer event	WP4, T4.2, CTA, support: all	An event that will open the way for building the capacity	M18-M34	✓ Done
Final dissemination event	WP5, T5.1, WR, support: all	Final event and dissemination of ROBIN's results	M36	✓ Done

On top of that, consortium partners organised seven additional events beyond those outlined in ROBIN's Grant Agreement, as detailed below:

- **Conference:** "Communities, Regions & Cities – The 'Bioeconomy in Action' in your Region", a launch event of Bioeconomy Ireland Week 2023, hosted by SRA.
- **Conference:** "Circular Bioeconomy Forum", organised by the Regional Government of Andalusia's Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development. The Robin project had a constant presence during the forum, through the Andalusian node and members of the Andalusian MARC. In addition to the Regional Ministry of Agriculture, as the organiser, representatives of IFAPA and CTA participated in some of the tables.
- **Workshop:** "*DemoDay Sustainable agricultural practices*", organised by the Instituto Andaluz de Investigación y Formación Agraria, Pesquera, Alimentaria y de la Producción Ecológica (IFAPA) focusing on sustainable agricultural practices in the field of bioeconomy for students.
- **Conference:** "You(th) in BIO.regions.SK", organised by Pedal Consulting.

- **Conference:** “Bioeconomy Conference”, organised by CAP and the Cajamar Foundation in Seville (Spain). ROBIN representatives from CAP and IFA participated in this event.
- **Workshop:** “BioConnect: linking theory and practice in the bioeconomy”, organised by Pedal Consulting within the BioGov.Net project activities.
- **Workshop:** “Unlocking Ireland’s Bioeconomy Potential: Policy Insights and Practical Tools for Regional Development”, a joint online event organised by ROBIN partners, MTU and SRA and ShapingBIO project focused on bioeconomy governance in Ireland.

A series of events has been organised to fulfil and promote both the project and its outcomes. This report highlights that all the project events have been completed as described above in the Table 7. All partners reported their dissemination actions, events and workshops took place in the dissemination reporting template (Figure 21 below).

No. of Action	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity (Please specify if the activity is ongoing, or if it is a one-off activity)	Number of attendees, participants, stakeholders, etc.	Number of publications, articles, etc.	Number of policy makers, etc.	Number of SMEs, etc.	Number of researchers, etc.	Number of civil society representatives, etc.	Number of other stakeholders, etc.														
1	2023/02	Virtual Event	Participation in online conference on the state of the art of the bioeconomy	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	2023/02	Workshop	Participation in workshop: 2nd ECR Coordinator and Support Workshop: Setting the scene	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	2023/03	Workshop	Participation in workshop: Virtual MAs workshop "Multi-Regional" - outcomes and	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	2023/03	On line	Participation in workshop: MARECOO2023	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	2023/03	On line	Participation in workshop: INTERCONNECTA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	2023/03	Workshop	Workshop on the state of the art of the bioeconomy	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	2023/03	Workshop	Workshop on the state of the art of the bioeconomy	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	2023/03	On line	Workshop on the state of the art of the bioeconomy	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 23. Dissemination reporting template

More specifically:

- **5 regional co-creation events (one in each region) comprised of 2 sessions for Task2.1 in April/May 2023 (M8/M9).**

5 two-part co-creation workshops were organised to first validate and prioritise key barriers, potentialities, and opportunities to be pursued in each ROBIN region and then to define improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s) (including novel business models and social measures). In total, five workshops have been organised, one in each region, overall engaging **69 stakeholders**, including the Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC) members of each pilot region and other regional Quadruple Helix stakeholders. Specifically:

- 15 policy makers,
- 17 researchers and academics,
- 12 civil society representatives,
- 23 business and SME representatives.
- 2 Other

Figure 24. Co-creation workshop series

- **Action Plan Workshop for Task 2.2 (M14)**

During the 3rd project meeting in Cork, Ireland (October 2023) all ROBIN partners discussed their ideas to shape regional Action Plans detailing the specific support actions that will be offered in their region.

Figure 25. Action Plan Workshop

- **Regional partners will run 2 stakeholder engagement events for T3.2 (M18 – M30)**

Alpha and Beta testing workshops were conducted to evaluate the ROBIN Toolbox in real-life settings across the target regions. These sessions provided valuable opportunities to gather direct feedback from users, assessing usability and functionality, as well as identifying areas for improvement. By engaging stakeholders in hands-on testing, the workshops ensured the Toolbox is both relevant and responsive to the actual needs of its potential users.

The testing process engaged five partner regions, in particular Andalusia (Spain), Baden-Württemberg (Germany), Central Macedonia (Greece), the Southern Region (Ireland), and Žilina (Slovakia), alongside eighteen external regions that participated through regional events and an open call for beta testing. Stakeholders from local governments, businesses, academia, and civil society actively contributed to both Alpha and Beta phases.

Figure 26. Stakeholder Engagement Workshops in target regions

- **Digital validation workshop for T3.3 (M25)**

A Validation Workshop was held in September 2024, following the Alpha Testing phase of the ROBIN Toolbox, to assess progress, gather feedback, and discuss potential improvements. The workshop was held online, focusing on evaluating the usability and effectiveness of the tools developed within the ROBIN project. It featured presentations, interactive feedback sessions, and open discussions with 31 participants, including members of the ROBIN Consortium, the Advisory Board, and the ROBIN MARC.

Figure 27. Validation Workshop with Advisory Board Members

- **2 mutual learning workshops and missions (DE and SK) for T4.2 (M18 – M34)**

The first Mutual Learning Workshop took place in September 2024 (Month 25) with more than 42 attendees, organised by ROBIN partner Corporación Tecnológica de Andalucía (CTA) and hosted at the premises of another ROBIN partner, Steinbeis Europa Zentrum, in Stuttgart. The workshop aimed to facilitate knowledge exchange among several EU-funded projects focused on developing tools to support the creation and/or consolidation of regional governance mechanisms in circular bioeconomy.

The second, titled “BioFUTURE – Knowledge sharing for unlocking the potential of bio-economy in Europe from the regional policy perspective“, took place on February 2025 (M30) and brought together over 85 participants. Corporación Tecnológica de Andalucía (CTA), representing the ROBIN project, has coordinated, in collaboration with three other European projects (BIOMODEL4REGIONS, BIOTRANSFORM, and ShapingBIO), this online workshop. It was focused on four key priority topics identified during the projects’ implementation with a dedicated and practical approach, and specifically:

- Governance and Policy Alignment
- Social and Regional Challenges and Public Awareness
- Cross-Sectoral Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement

- Environmental Impact and Resource Efficiency

Figure 28. Mutual Learning Workshops

5.7 Train-the-Trainer Workshop

The **Train-the-Trainer Workshop: Scaling the Bioeconomy through ROBIN's Toolbox, Policies, and Strategies** took place on May 14th as part of ROBIN's Final Event. The workshop focused on the design, deployment, and analysis of governance models and policies, highlighting both the theoretical foundations and practical application of the tools developed within the ROBIN project. Its main objective was to equip regional stakeholders with the knowledge and strategies needed to effectively implement circular bioeconomy initiatives.

A key highlight of the event was the active participation of ROBIN's five partner regions - Andalusia (ES), Baden-Württemberg (DE), Central Macedonia (EL), Southern Region (IE), and Žilina (SK) - who shared their experiences, insights, and lessons learned in applying the ROBIN Toolbox in their respective regional contexts.

Figure 29. Screenshot from the T-t-T Workshop

5.8 Joint Final Conference

WR, as the dissemination manager of the ROBIN project, in collaboration with five other Horizon Europe Projects - MainstreamBIO, SCALE-UP, RuralBioUP, BioRural, and Biomodel4Regions - organised ROBIN's final event, titled **“European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference: Policy, Innovation and Collaboration for a Sustainable Future.”** The event took place on May

13th in Brussels, Belgium, and was hosted in a hybrid format, **attracting 180 participants both online and on-site.**

The conference brought together a diverse audience of policymakers, researchers, innovators, regional leaders, and farmers to engage in meaningful dialogue on advancing sustainability, resilience, and inclusivity in Europe’s rural regions through the circular bioeconomy. The agenda featured keynote speeches, panel discussions, and collaborative sessions addressing policy frameworks, regional innovation strategies, and actionable pathways for bioeconomy deployment.

A key **milestone of the event** was the **signing of a Memorandum of Collaboration (MoC) by the five ROBIN regions** - Andalusia, Baden-Württemberg, Central Macedonia, the Southern Region of Ireland, and Žilina Region. Through this agreement, the regions formally committed to strengthening their collaboration, exchanging innovations, and scaling impactful solutions to accelerate the circular bioeconomy transition across Europe.

Schedule	Sessions
09:00-09:30	Welcoming Breakfast & Registration
09:30-10:00	Michael Losch, European Commission - Coordinator for Bioeconomy Manco Rupp, Biobased Industries Consortium
10:00-11:20	Fire-pitching of hosting projects MainstreamBIO ROBIN Biorural BIOMODELREGIONS SCALE UP RuralBioUP
11:20-11:30	Coffee break
11:30-12:30	Panel discussion Diverse Perspectives on Bioeconomy: Exploring how different approaches complement each other to enhance the EU's bioeconomy
12:30-13:30	Lunch Buffet
13:30-15:00	Tools for Advancing the EU's Bioeconomy: Supporting local communities, policymakers, and entrepreneurs in adopting sustainable practices
15:00-15:15	Coffee break
15:15-16:30	Panel discussion Inspiring Change Through Success Stories: Real-world applications driving innovation and adoption across regions
16:30-16:45	Signing Memorandum of Collaboration among ROBIN regions (Andalusia, Zilina, Central Macedonia, Southern Regional Assembly and Baden-Wuerttemberg)
16:45-17:15	Wrap up and Networking

Schedule	Sessions
08:50-09:30	Welcoming Breakfast & Registration
09:30-11:00	ROOM 4.4 Keynote speech: Pathway towards the new EU Bioeconomy Strategy (15') F. Calikowski, DG Research and Innovation, European Commission Presentation of joint policy observations from RuralBioUp, MainstreamBio, SCALE UP and BioRural (40') Panel discussion and Q&A session (35')
11:00-11:15	Coffee break
11:15-13:30	ROOM 5.3 Policy round table "Implementation of small-scale BIO based solutions across rural Europe" organised by MainstreamBIO
11:15-13:30	ROOM 3.4 ROBIN Train-the-Trainer Workshop: Scaling the Bioeconomy Through ROBIN's Toolbox, Policies, and Strategies
11:15-13:30	ROOM 6.4 International Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop "Building Bridges in Bioeconomy: From Regional Partnerships to Future Pathways for Europe" organised by RuralBioUp and BiomodelRegions
13:30-14:30	Light lunch

Figure 30. ROBIN's Final Event Agenda

Figure 31. ROBIN's Consortium Partners

White Research supported partners for the dissemination and engagement needs of these events, when needed. WR requested some brief information from the partners hosting the events, in combination with photos or other materials, to promote the event through ROBIN’s SMAs.

ROBIN partners successfully organised 29 workshops and events, exceeding the KPI target of 22.

5.9 Participation to external events

ROBIN partners have attended external events such as conferences and workshops with the aim to reach a wide audience relevant to ROBIN’s objectives. During these events the partners:

- Presented the project (concept, approach, etc.);
- Promoted the project’s results;
- Promoted ROBIN's actions and events;
- Established synergies and contacts with relevant projects and initiatives;
- Engaged relevant stakeholders in the project’s activities;
- Promoted the project’s dissemination channels (website, SMAs, etc.).

The partners who participated in external events always followed the visual identity of the project and used the official promotional material (leaflet, poster, .ppt template, etc.). In case of participation in an external event with the aim to present ROBIN, partners sent the final presentation to WR **at least 5 working days prior to the event**. In addition, the partners always informed WR in advance regarding their participation in an external event to be appropriately disseminated through the project’s dissemination accounts. Finally, after actual participation, partners filled in the reporting template (Annex I) and sent it back to WR.

An indicative list of identified conferences and events is provided in Table 8 below:

Table 8. Indicative list of external events where ROBIN partners have participated

No.	Event title	Date	Brief description of ROBIN participation
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1	CBE-JU, BIC, CEE2ACT – Promoting Bioeconomy in Greece	April 2024	Under the auspices of the CEE2ACT, this event aimed to bring together professionals, researchers, and enthusiasts from various sectors of the wider field of Bioeconomy. The goal was to explore and discuss the latest developments, challenges, and opportunities in the field, as well as co-design the next steps towards drawing a National Bioeconomy strategy for Greece. The event featured insightful presentations, interactive discussions, and networking opportunities, all conducted entirely in English.
2	Challenges of the Bioeconomy in Andalusia and Spain	May 2024	Workshop organised by the Almería technology center to discuss the implementation of bioeconomy in Andalusia and Spain.
3	Bioeconomía en el sector olivarero como palanca de transformación económica y social / Bioeconomy in the olive sector as a lever for economic and social transformation	June 2024	The meeting, framed in the European project SCALE-UP, brought together more than 80 attendees who analysed the development opportunities offered by the bioeconomy of the olive sector in Andalusia.
4	Innovation Meetup Bioeconomy	June 2024	The goal of the Meetup was to discuss the ongoing and planned initiatives in bioeconomy and establish new connections in this field. Several invited start-up founders, entrepreneurs, innovators presented their innovative activities, solutions or approaches that are in line with the principles of the circular bioeconomy. The details, activities and goals of the ROBIN project was presented by PEDAL. The presentation about the ROBIN project was heard by high-level Slovak policy-makers.
5	6th international conference on Changing Cities	June 2024	Q-Plan presented the Environmental Protection Planning Tool of ROBIN and described its usefulness for European Urban and Regional Authorities.
6	5th international Bioeconomy conference 2024 in Baden-Württemberg	September 2024	Participation to a session on "Start-Up Hilfen, Tipps und Tricks" which ROBIN project was shortly presented.

7	European Week of Regions and Cities	October 2024	ROBIN participated in the conference by distributing its leaflets during the Circular Economy Innovation Valley session, aiming to raise awareness of the project among attendees.
8	Bioeconomy Marketplace Workshop	October 2024	Robin project was presented by CTA in this workshop which was designed as a marketplace to showcase the achievements of nine RuralBioUp regional hubs and six Biomodel4regions pilot regions. Participants explored key results and outputs through engaging poster presentations, highlighting innovative local bioeconomy strategies and action plans to promote bioeconomy at a local level.
9	CCRI 3rd Coordination and Support Workshop: Making circular investments pay off for cities and regions	November 2024	ROBIN project participated in the pitching session and in two thematic Working Groups sessions: - Circular Bioeconomy - Circular Resource Management
10	National government Bioeconomy Implementation and Development Group committee meeting	November 2024	ROBIN presentation delivered to the national bioeconomy oversight committee on actions and progress to date by SRA to promote bioeconomy in the southern region of Ireland.
11	BioCircular Summit	February 2025	The ROBIN project was highlighted as a key initiative for the development of the circular bioeconomy. Furthermore, ROBIN received the award for the best public-private collaboration initiative in the field of bioeconomy.
12	Bioeconomy in Tipperary	April 2025	Presentation of EU Projects on bioeconomy currently engaged in by Irish Bioeconomy Foundation and Tipperary County Council, followed by workshop/SWOT analysis of bioeconomy in the region.
13	Europe Day & 10th Anniversary of the establishment of the Southern Regional Assembly celebration	May 2025	The event addressed by Minister of State for Local Government and Planning, and included a showcase of Projects in which the SRA is involved, including ROBIN. An information stand dedicated to the ROBIN project was set up at the event, where brochures were distributed and the project's promotional video was showcased.

ROBIN partners participated in 58 external events both virtually and physically. This metric exceeds the KPI of 15 events. In these events, partners played central roles, such as presenters, maximising the project's visibility. It is evident that participation in external events has proven to be one of the most effective means of disseminating ROBIN to both the EU community and regional audiences, while also establishing a robust audience base. **Even though ROBIN achieved its official KPI within the first few months of the project, the team continued to actively participate in external events. This ongoing engagement had a positive impact on additional KPIs, such as increased views of the promotional video, higher website traffic, and growth in social media followers.**

5.10 Academic Publications and Public Deliverables

Scientific publications were important channels for presenting ROBIN's outcomes to academic, research, and industrial target audiences. Thus, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the project's results in their own work contributed to disseminating the project further.

To ensure the metric was accomplished, WR developed a clear plan to monitor scientific publication efforts in collaboration with all partners. A publication matrix was created on the project's shared MS Teams platform, allowing partners to report their activities, identify collaboration opportunities, and track the status of submitted papers.

ROBIN partners successfully managed to publish four open access academic publications, exceeding the initial KPI target of 3. All academic publications are available to ROBIN's website [here](#).

Table 9. List of ROBIN academic publications

No.	Authors	Title of paper / topic	Title of Journal	Status of paper	Links
1	Samir Sayadi, Mar Cátedra, Carmen Capote, Carlos Parra, Guillermo García, Milagros Argüelles, Esther Ortiz	Análisis estratégico de la implantación de la bioeconomía circular en Andalucía a través del análisis DAFO	C3 - BIOECONOMY, Circular and Sustainable Bioeconomy	Published	Link
2	Fátima Rojas-Serrano, Guillermo García-García, Carlos Parra-López, Samir Sayadi-Gmada	Sustainability, circular economy and bioeconomy: A conceptual review and integration into the notion of sustainable circular bioeconomy	NEW MEDIT	Published	Link

3	Alexandros Skondras, Stefanos Nastis, Ifigeneia Skalidi, Asterios Theofilou, Aikaterini Bakousi, Thomas Mone, Zoi Eirini Tsifodimou, James Gaffey, Robert Ludgate, Tracey O'Connor, Dragica Grozdanic, Breda O'Dwyer, Eleni Pappa, Kallitsa Pantazi, Efstratios Stylianidis	Governance Strategies for Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy Development in Europe: Insights and Typologies	Sustainability	Published	Link
4	Samir Sayadi Gmada, Mar Cátedra, Carmen Capote, Carlos Parra-López, María García, Carmen Ronchel, Rafael Dueñas-Sánchez, Esther Ortiz, Milagros Argüelles and José Luis Cruz	Driving Sustainability: Circular Bioeconomy and Governance in Andalusia (Southern Spain)	Sustainability	Published	Link

The deliverables section on ROBIN’s website designed to host all of the project’s public deliverables. After communicating with the project officer (PO), the PO permission to ROBIN team to publicly upload and distribute these deliverables. Consequently, each time a public deliverable was submitted, it was uploaded to the website and shared via the project’s social media channels. The dissemination of these deliverables focused on enhancing the visibility of the project’s scientific results, with a primary focus on academic and policy-oriented audiences. The dissemination through social media allowed a broader audience to comprehend the fundamental concepts and purposes of each deliverable.

Figure 32. ROBIN's public deliverables uploaded to the website

The following reports are currently available on our website:

- D1.1 Typology of Bioeconomy Governance Models
- D1.2 Good Governance Practices
- D1.3 Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions
- D2.1 Typology of Regional Models
- D2.2 ROBIN Regional Action Plans
- D2.3 ROBIN Toolbox
- D3.1 ROBIN Toolbox Validation Plans
- D3.2 Report on ROBIN Toolbox Validation and Update
- D4.1 Outcomes, Impacts and Perceptions Change
- D5.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan - Initial Version
- D5.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results - Interim Version
- D6.2 Data Management Plan - Initial Version

Throughout the duration of the ROBIN project, all partners are invited to produce press and media releases, articles in mass media, and presentations on TV or radio, or other media. The aim of all these efforts was to increase the project's visibility and publicity and the potential to reach out to stakeholders outside of the consortium.

To promote the project, partners have made significant contributions, including publishing articles, issuing press releases, and even presenting ROBIN on radio shows and podcasts. A **total of 24 press releases** were issued to inform stakeholders about the project's key actions and results.

5.11 Networks and Synergies

General overview

ROBIN's Task 5.3 leader was Steinbeis 2i GmbH (S2i). ROBIN aimed to foster collaboration with other relevant projects, initiatives and networks through a multifaceted approach, encompassing the following strategies:

- Organising online and on-site bilateral and/or multilateral meetings to foster expanded cooperation and communication,
- Displaying mutual links and logos on the ROBIN website within dedicated sub-categories such as "[related projects](#)" and "[related initiatives](#)",
- Disseminating (joint) announcements, including significant events, across various social media platforms,
- Engaging in social media interactions by liking, sharing, reposting, retweeting, and commenting on each other's posts,
- Generating announcements on external websites to promote noteworthy events,
- Collaborating in the organisation of joint events, such as workshops or conferences, involving relevant stakeholders,
- Extending invitations to representatives from other projects and initiatives to participate in (ROBIN) organised events,

- Participating in events from other projects and initiatives to share updates, insights and results about ROBIN,
- Coordinating joint sessions at conferences for the presentation of collective results.
- Co-authoring and publishing mutual blog posts, scientific publications and policy recommendations to contribute to shared knowledge.

At the beginning of the project, an online list (excel file) was created by Task leader S2i to collect relevant projects, initiatives and networks suggested by all partners. This listing was a living document and partners added new projects and initiatives throughout the project duration opening new opportunities for collaboration and synergies. At the end of the project, the consortium had gathered 61 suggestions and cooperated effectively with 31 projects, networks and initiatives.

Collaboration agreements

To formalise these collaborative efforts, a bilateral collaboration agreement template was drafted (see Annex II). This document served to articulate, in written form, the anticipated aspects of collaboration between projects, ensuring clarity and alignment in mutual objectives.

Bilateral agreements were signed with the following projects:

- RBA projects (original members: [BioRural](#), [MainstreamBIO](#), [P2Green](#), [RELIEF](#), [RuralBioUp](#), [SCALE-UP](#), [COOPID](#), [BioModel4Regions](#), [ShapingBio](#), [CEE2ACT](#))
- [BIOMODEL4REGIONS](#)
- [SUSTCERT4BIOBASED](#)
- [NENUPHAR](#)
- [Biorefine Cluster Europe](#)

However, in many cases, we cooperated with projects and initiatives without having such formal collaboration agreements. The subsequent sections detail the concrete collaboration efforts and results, starting with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI), then with networks and finally with individual projects.

Collaboration with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)

ROBIN established from the beginning contact with the CCRI coordination and support office (CCRI-CSO). **ROBIN is a [CCRI project](#)**. This means that there is a dedicated fiche about the project on the CCRI website (see Figure 33). S2i provided information and made sure to update the project fiche whenever needed.

Figure 33: Screenshot of ROBIN project fiche on the CCRI website

Collaboration framework

In November 2023, S2i defined with the CCRI coordination and support office (CCRI-CSO) a collaboration plan, which is summarised in Table 10 below.

Table 10: Plan of collaboration and input to the CCRI

#	What	Timeline	Quantification
1	Input in the CCRI site “ <i>Tools and methods</i> ” of each of the components of the toolbox	Final version after WP3 testing done	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 20 Governance Models - 10 Good practices - 3 ROBIN Tools - 47 support actions
2	Invitation to EU regions to participate in ROBIN WP3 and WP4 workshops Invitations will be published in the “ <i>Events</i> ” section of the CCRI website	According to WP3 and WP4 time plan for the workshops	Invitation to at least 5 workshops

3	Participation of ROBIN representatives in future CCRI events (annual conferences, TWG meetings)	When planned by CCRI	At least 2 onsite and 3 online meetings
4	Invitation to EU regions to participate in events organised by ROBIN partners Invitations will be published in the “ <i>Events</i> ” section of the CCRI website	When informed by ROBIN partners	at least 10 invitations
5	Share information about publications from ROBIN partners in the CCRI website	When the publications are ready according to the project plan	At least 3 scientific publications and 1 white paper

S2i monitored the progress of the collaboration plan via a dedicated table (see Figure 34), made sure that the defined KPIs were on track, regularly asked partners to provide information about workshops/events they organised in order to forward this information to the CCRI-CSO.

During the monthly meetings as well as during the project meetings, S2i informed partners about what had been done in the past month, what was currently ongoing and/or planned but also asked partners for support or input on an *ad hoc* basis.

The next paragraphs develop each of the five points of the collaboration plan.

Stand: 30.06.2025

CCRI-ROBIN cooperation framework

agreed between Alejandra Campos (S2i/ROBIN), Jan Wynarski (ECORYS/CCRI) and Bas Verbeek (EGEN/CCRI) in November 2023

Legend: ongoing/planned activity or task
completed activity or task

Cooperation type	What	Target	#	Title	Responsible PP	Date	Deadline	
Invite EU regions to participate in ROBIN WP3 and WP4 workshops (to be published in CCRI event site)	Invitation to ROBIN workshops	>5	1	Workshop on Bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg focusing on financing (Workshop zu Bioökonomie in Baden-Württemberg mit Schwerpunkt Finanzen) (WP3)	S2i	18.07.2024	-	
			2	First mutual learning workshop (WP4)	CTA/S2i	09.10.2024	-	
			3	Towards 2030: Developing a Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model for our Communities, Cities and Regions	SRA, MTU	15.10.2024	-	
			4	Together for the Slovak bioeconomy (WP3)	PEDAL, RAZK	04.12.2024	-	
			5	Austausch über die Entwicklung von Bioökonomie-Strategien und deren Monitoring in urbanen und ländlichen Räumen (WP3)	S2i	06.02.2025	-	
			6	Second mutual learning workshop (WP4)	CTA/PEDAL	19.02.2025	-	
			7	Beta testing workshop in Thessaloniki (WP3)	RCM	27.02.2025	-	
			8	Workshop in Malaga (WP3)	CAP/IFA	13.03.2025	-	
			9					
Participate in future CCRI events (annual conferences, TWG meetings)	participation in CCRI events	>2 onsite	1	CCRI workshop 2023 in Brussels	S2i, RCM	09.11.2023	-	
			2	CCRI workshop 2024 in Brussels	S2i, WR, RCM	13.11.2024	-	
			3	TWG C-BIO first workshop	WR	22.03.2024	-	
			4	2nd CCRI associated partner workshop on "Involvement of the private sector in circular economy and circular systemic solutions"	S2i	30.04.2024	-	
Invite EU regions to participate in ROBIN events (to be published in CCRI events site)	invitation to ROBIN events	>10	1	You(th) in and for bioregions	PEDAL	13.03.2024	-	
			2	Careers and opportunities in the Bioeconomy	Q-PLAN	14.03.2024	-	
			3	Final conference	WR	13-14.05.2025	-	
			4	Train the Trainer	CTA	14.05.2025	-	
Share information about ROBIN publications on CCRI website	Scientific publications	>3	1	"Unlocking Ireland's Bioeconomy Potential: Policy Insights and Practical Tools for Regional Development" webinar	MTU/SRA	01.05.2025	-	
			2	Rojas-Serrano, F.; Garcia-Garcia, G.; Parra-López, C.; Sayadi, S. (2024) "Sustainability, circular economy and bioeconomy: A conceptual review and integration into the notion of sustainable circular bioeconomy". Review: Mediterranean journal of economics, agriculture and environment (New Medit). https://newmedit.iamb.it/2024/04/02/sustainability-circular-economy-and-bioeconomy-a-conceptual-review-and-integration-into-the-notion-of-sustainable-circular-bioeconomy/	CAP/IFA	April 2024 (M20)	M35	
			3	Sayadi, S.; Cátedra, M.; Capote, C.; Parra-López, C.; García-García, G.; Argüelles, M.; Ortiz, E. (2023). "Análisis estratégico de la implantación de la bioeconomía circular en Andalucía a través del análisis DAFO (Strategic analysis of the implementation of circular bioeconomy in Andalusia through SWOT analysis)". Review: C3-BIOECONOMY: Circular and Sustainable Bioeconomy, 4: 75-93. https://journals.uco.es/bioeconomy/article/view/16294/15000	CAP/IFA	Dec 2023 (M16)	M35	
			4	Governance Strategies for Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy Development in Europe: Insights and Typologies by Alexandros Skondras 1, Stefanos A. Nastis, Ifigeneia Skalidi, Asterios Theofilou, Aikaterini Bakousi, Thomas Mone, Zoi Eirini Tsifodimou, James Gaffey, Robert Ludgate, Tracey O'Connor, Dragica Grozdanic, Breda O'Dwyer, Eleni Pappa, Kalitsa Pantazi and Efstratios Stylianidis https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/16/12/5140	AUTH, MTU	June 2024 (M22)	M35	
White Paper	1	1	1	Driving Sustainability: Circular Bioeconomy and Governance in Andalusia (Southern Spain) Samir Sayadi Gmada; Mar Cátedra; Carmen Capote; Carlos Parra-López; María García; Carmen Ronchel; Rafael Dueñas-Sánchez; Esther Ortiz; Milagros Argüelles; José Luis Cruz Sustainability 2025, Volume 17, Issue 7, 3128 https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/7/3128	CAP/IFA	April 2025 (M32)	M35	
			2		PED	July 2025 (M35)	M35	
NEW / on top	Success Stories	>3	1	satellite event Thessaloniki - Careers and opportunities in the Bioeconomy	Q-PLAN	14.03.2024	-	
			2	satellite event Nitra - You(th) in and for bioregions	PEDAL	13.03.2024	-	
			3					
			4					
			5					

Figure 34: Overview of the collaboration with CCRI

1) Provision of input to CCRI website

According to ROBIN Grant Agreement and Description of Action, KPI-3 foresaw that the consortium would contribute to the database of the CCRI by providing at least 50 good practices.

After the end of the beta testing and the finetuning of the Toolbox, S2i informed CCRI-CSO that the ROBIN Toolbox was finalised. In order to not overload their website with too many different support materials, CCRI-CSO decided to create a single fiche on the ROBIN Toolbox for the Knowledge part of the CCRI website (*tools and methods* section). In addition, the fiche of the ROBIN project will be updated to include the hyperlinks of all deliverables and of the different Toolbox components including the 31 good practices and 20 governance models. In doing so, we ensured to fulfil KPI-3 and provide over 50 good practices to the CCRI database.

2) Invitation to EU regions to participate in ROBIN WP3 and WP4 workshops

ROBIN consortium had agreed to **invite EU regions to at least 5 workshops** organised in the frame of WP3 and WP4 activities. When they organised local workshops, ROBIN partners prepared an event fiche (based on a template provided by the CCRI-CSO) and S2i forwarded it to the communication team of the CCRI-CSO. The events were then added to the CCRI calendar (in the [Events](#) section). By the end of the project, ROBIN had sent 8 workshops invitations.

Below is the list of the 8 ROBIN workshops that were promoted on the CCRI events section and for which EU regions were invited to join (Table 11). The hyperlinks lead to the CCRI calendar.

Table 11: ROBIN WP3/WP4 workshops in the CCRI calendar

#	Workshop title	Responsible Partner	Date
1	<u>Workshop on Bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg focusing on financing (WP3)</u>	S2i	18 July 2024
2	<u>First mutual learning workshop (WP4)</u>	CTA/S2i	09 October 2024
3	<u>Towards 2030: Developing a Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model for our Communities, Cities and Regions (WP3/WP4)</u>	SRA, MTU	15 October 2024
4	<u>Together for the Slovak bioeconomy (WP3/WP4)</u>	PEDAL, RAZK	04 December 2024
5	<u>Exchange on the development of bioeconomy strategies and their monitoring in urban and rural areas (WP3/WP4)</u>	S2i	06 February 2025
6	<u>Second mutual learning workshop (WP4)</u>	CTA/PEDAL	19 February 2025
7	<u>Beta testing validation workshop in Thessaloniki (WP3/WP4)</u>	RCM	27 February 2025
8	<u>Exchange of regional experiences in circular bioeconomy within the framework of the ROBIN project (WP3/WP4)</u>	CAP/IFA	13 March 2025

3) Participation of ROBIN representatives in CCRI events

ROBIN representatives – especially S2i – regularly participated in general meetings organised by the CCRI-CSO as well as the sessions of the Thematic Working Group (TWG) on Circular Bioeconomy. ROBIN successfully fulfilled the expectations to attend at least 2 onsite and 3 online meetings. Table 12 provides an overview of the meetings attended by ROBIN representatives.

Table 12: CCRI meetings where ROBIN was represented

#	Date	Location	ROBIN repr.	Description
1	19.10.2022	Brussels	S2i	First CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop
2	27.10.2022	Online	S2i	First CCRI Webinar where the CCRI methodology for implementation of circular economy was presented
3	08.03.2023	Online	S2i	First meeting of the CCRI Thematic Working Group (TWG) on Circular Bioeconomy
4	08.11.2023	Brussels	S2i, RCM	CCRI General Conference with ROBIN poster presentation
5	09.11.2023	Brussels	S2i, RCM	Participation in the discussion of the TWG “Circular bioeconomy”
6	22.03.2024	online	WR	First workshop of the TWG Circular bioeconomy 2024
7	30.04.2024	online	S2i	Second CCRI associated partner workshop on "Involvement of the private sector in circular economy and circular systemic solutions"
8	31.05.2024	Online	S2i	Second workshop of the TWG Circular bioeconomy 2024
9	13.11.2024	Brussels	S2i, WR, RCM	General conference & thematic working group session “Circular bioeconomy”
10	16.01.2025	online	S2i	First workshop of the TWG Circular bioeconomy 2025

4) Invitation to EU regions to participate in events organised by ROBIN partners

In addition to WP3 and WP4 workshops, ROBIN partners organized further local events. We had agreed to forward 10 invitations. However, ROBIN partners did not organise so many events. Following the same procedure, S2i forwarded all event fiches to the CCRI-CSO communication team.

Below is the list of the 5 ROBIN events that were promoted on the CCRI events section and for which EU regions were invited to join (Table 13).

Table 13: ROBIN events in the CCRI calendar

#	Workshop title	Responsible Partner	Date
1	<u>You(th) in and for bioregions</u>	PED	13 March 2024
2	<u>Careers and opportunities in the Bioeconomy</u>	QPL	14 March 2024
3	<u>European Rural Circular Bioeconomy conference (ROBIN final conference)</u>	WR	13 May 2025
4	<u>ROBIN Train the Trainer</u>	CTA	14 May 2025
5	<u>'Unlocking Ireland's Bioeconomy Potential: Policy Insights and Practical Tools for Regional Development' webinar'</u>	MTU/SRA	01 May 2025

5) Share information about publications from ROBIN partners in the CCRI website

A final aspect of the collaboration plan with CCRI consisted in sharing publications from ROBIN partners. S2i transmitted 4 scientific publications to the CCRI-CSO and shared the ROBIN White Paper and 4 policy briefs prepared by PED. We therefore fulfilled the expectation of sharing information about at least 3 scientific publications and 1 white paper.

Table 14: ROBIN publications shared with CCRI-CSO

#	Publication title	Responsible Partner
1	Rojas-Serrano, F.; Garcia-Garcia, G.; Parra-López, C.; Sayadi, S. (2024) "Sustainability, circular economy and bioeconomy: A conceptual review and integration into the notion of sustainable circular bioeconomy". <i>Revue: Mediterranean journal of economics, agriculture and environment (New Medit)</i> . https://newmedit.iamb.it/2024/04/02/sustainability-circular-economy-and-bioeconomy-a-conceptual-review-and-integration-into-the-notion-of-sustainable-circular-bioeconomy/	CAP, IFA
2	Sayadi, S.; Cátedra, M.; Capote, C.; Parra-López, C.; García-García, G.; Argüelles, M.; Ortiz, E. (2023). "Análisis estratégico de la implantación de la bioeconomía circular en Andalucía a través del análisis DAFO (Strategic analysis of the implementation of circular bioeconomy in Andalusia through SWOT analysis)". <i>Revue: C3-BIOECONOMY: Circular and Sustainable Bioeconomy</i> , 4: 75-93. https://journals.uco.es/bioeconomy/article/view/16294/15000	CAP, IFA
3	<i>Governance Strategies for Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy Development in Europe: Insights and Typologies</i> by Alexandros	AUTh, MTU

	Skondras 1, Stefanos A. Nastis, Ifigeneia Skalidi, Asterios Theofilou, Aikaterini Bakousi, Thomas Mone, Zoi Eirini Tsifodimou, James Gaffey, Robert Ludgate , Tracey O'Connor, Dragica Grozdanic, Breda O'Dwyer, Eleni Pappa, Kallitsa Pantazi and Efstratios Stylianidis https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/16/12/5140	
4	<i>Driving Sustainability: Circular Bioeconomy and Governance in Andalusia (Southern Spain)</i> . Samir Sayadi Gmada; Mar Cátedra; Carmen Capote; Carlos Parra-López; María García; Carmen Ronchel; Rafael Dueñas-Sánchez; Esther Ortiz; Milagros Argüelles; José Luis Cruz Sustainability 2025, Volume 17, Issue 7, 3128 https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/7/3128	CAP, IFA
5	<i>White Paper</i> https://robin-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/ROBIN-White-Paper.pdf	PED
6	<i>4 policy briefs</i> https://robin-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/ROBIN-Policy-Brief.pdf	PED

6) Miscellaneous

In addition to the 5 aspects mentioned above, we would like highlight two further elements:

1. The ROBIN consortium shared 2 “success stories” with the CCRI-CSO based on the satellite events of the Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival organised in Nitra on 13 March 2024 by PED and in Thessaloniki on 14 March 2024 by QPL.
2. S2i ensured the promotion of the Open Call for ROBIN Beta Testing via the CCRI newsletter (Issue of October 2024) as can be seen on the screenshot on the right hand side.

CCRI Newsletter: October 2024

Dear Clementine

Welcome to the **26th issue** of the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) Newsletter.

In this issue we explore the outcomes of the DECISO annual conference, invite you to take part in the CCRI's ROBIN Project beta testing phase, and celebrate CCRI Project Circ-Boost's recent success developing sustainable concrete from recycled materials for new builds in Czechia.

Collaboration with networks

ROBIN also collaborated with networks, especially the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA) and the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet).

Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)

ROBIN is one of the founding project members of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance ([RBA](#)). The RBA is a cluster of 20 projects (stand of August 2025), aiming to speed up the growth of bioeconomy by

sharing knowledge on project outcomes and supporting dissemination and communication activities related to the existing knowledge of bioeconomy. The list of the project members (besides ROBIN) is shown in Table 15.

Table 15: Projects member of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)

No.	Project	Website
1	BioRural	https://biorural.eu/
2	MainstreamBIO	https://mainstreambio-project.eu/
3	P2Green	https://p2green.eu/
4	RELIEF	https://relief.uop.gr/
5	RuralBioUp	https://www.ruralbioup.eu/
6	SCALE-UP	www.scaleup-bioeconomy.eu/
7	COOPID	https://coopid.eu/
8	ShapingBio	https://www.shapingbio.eu/
9	BIOMODEL4REGIONS	https://www.biomodel4regions.eu/
10	CEE2ACT	https://www.cee2act.eu/
11	BIO2REG	https://bio2reg.eu/
12	BBioNets	https://bbionets.eu/
13	Agriloop	https://www.agriloop-project.eu/
14	Brilian	https://brilian.eu/
15	BioINSouth	https://www.bioinsouth.eu/
16	FUTURAL	https://futural-project.eu/
17	ARGONAUT	https://argonaut-project.eu/
18	ERDN	http://erdn.eu/therbn-a-new-horizon-europe-project-kicked-off/
19	Rural BioReFarmeries	https://ruralbiorefarmeries.eu/

In the frame of RBA, S2i regularly participated in the virtual meetings that are organised every second months. During these meetings, project representatives share about upcoming events and activities and actively seek synergies with other member projects. S2i promoted ROBIN open call, the two mutual learning workshops as well as its regional workshops and events.

Here are furthermore 2 concrete examples of collaboration in the frame of the RBA:

1. The **Second ROBIN mutual learning workshop** titled 'BioFUTURE: Knowledge sharing for unlocking the potential of bioeconomy in Europe from the regional policy perspective' co-organised with ShapingBio and BIOTRANSFORM on 19 February 2025
2. **ROBIN final conference** titled European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference organised jointly with 5 other EU projects (MainstreamBIO, SCALE-UP, BioRural, BIOMODEL4REGIONS and RuralBioUP – all RBA members) on 13-14 May 2025 in Brussels.

The 2 screenshots below from the 10th and 12th RBA regular meetings (28 January 2025 and 09 May 2025) show the exchange of information about upcoming events.

European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet)

ROBIN was included as partner project in the *European Bioeconomy Network*. S2i made sure to promote ROBIN events by adding them in the EuBioNet calendar (*News and Events* section). The screenshot below (Figure 35) shows for instance the event fiches for 2 ROBIN events: our second mutual learning workshop on 19 February 2025 and a regional workshop organised in Baden-Württemberg on 06 February 2025.

Figure 35: ROBIN – Project member of the European Bioeconomy Network

Collaboration with individual projects

The ROBIN project/consortium exchanged and collaborated with various individual projects. S2i – as Task leader for synergies – organised and/or participated in bilateral and multilateral meetings with project representatives throughout the project duration to discuss and implement specific collaborations. The following table provides an overview of the results.

Table 16: Overview of ROBIN collaboration with individual projects

#	Project	Bilateral meetings	Concrete collaboration
1	BIOMODEL4REGIONS	28.02.2024, 30.04.2024, 11.09.2024, 16.09.2024, 21.10.2024, 18.11.2024, 02.12.2024, 26.02.2025	ROBIN participation in CEE2ACT & BM4R <u>Joint Webinar</u> "Stakeholder engagement in bioeconomy related projects" (22.06.2023) <u>First ROBIN mutual learning workshop</u> (09.10.2024) <u>BioFUTURE Mutual learning workshop</u> (19.02.2025) <u>European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference</u> (13.05.2025) <u>Joint Policy Recommendations</u>
2	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	04.03.2024, 04.07.2024, 14.11.2024, 13.02.2025	N/A

3	BIOTRANSFORM	26.02.2024, 08.04.2024, 06.05.2024, 10.09.2024, 18.11.2024, 19.11.2024, 02.12.2024, 14.01.2025, 26.02.2025, 15.05.2025	<p><u><i>First ROBIN mutual learning workshop</i></u> (09.10.2024)</p> <p><u><i>BioFUTURE Mutual learning workshop</i></u> (19.02.2025)</p> <p>Participation of ROBIN to BIOTRANSFORM final event in Brussels (13.03.2025)</p> <p>Participation of ROBIN to a BIOTRANSFORM local event (20.03.2025)</p> <p><u><i>Joint Policy Recommendations</i></u></p>
4	SUSTRACK	26.02.2025	<p><u><i>First ROBIN mutual learning workshop</i></u> (09.10.2024)</p> <p><u><i>Joint Policy Recommendations</i></u></p>
5	BIOLOC	N/A	<p>Participation of BIOLOC in 3 ROBIN regional workshops in Stuttgart (02.05.2023, 18.07.2024, 06.02.2025)</p> <p>Presentation of ROBIN Toolbox during BIOLOC hub meeting (03.12.2024)</p> <p>Participation of ROBIN in BIOLOC regional workshop in Stuttgart (18.06.2025)</p>
6	RIBES	05.06.2024, 17.10.2024	N/A
7	BioGov.Net	19.11.2024	Participation in regional workshop in Stuttgart (06.02.2025)
8	Hubs4Circularity	N/A	<p>ROBIN provided content regarding the ROBIN tools for the knowledge platform of Hubs4Circularity:</p> <p><u>https://www.h4c-community.eu/knowledge-platform/</u></p>
9	NENUPHAR	21.11.2024	ROBIN partner (RCM) filled NENUPHAR questionnaire on governance models
10	DIVAGRI	25.02.2025	Joint webinar (planned)
11	ShapingBio	30.04.2024, 16.09.2024, 21.10.2024, 18.11.2024,	ShapingBio presentation during ROBIN regional workshop in Stuttgart (18.07.2024)

		02.12.2024, 26.02.2025	ShapingBio participated in regional workshop in Stuttgart (06.02.2025) <u>BioFUTURE Mutual learning workshop</u> (19.02.2025) Joint event <u>‘Unlocking Ireland’s Bioeconomy Potential: Policy Insights and Practical Tools for Regional Development’</u> (01.05.2025)
12	CEE2ACT	N/A	ROBIN participation in CEE2ACT & BM4R <u>Joint Webinar</u> "Stakeholder engagement in bioeconomy related projects" (22.06.2023) <u>First ROBIN mutual learning workshop</u> (09.10.2024)
13	BioINSouth	20.11.2024, 24.02.2025	N/A
14	BIO2REG	06.08.2024, 12.09.2024	BIO2REG participation in 2 regional workshops in Stuttgart (18.07.2024, 06.02.2025)
15	BioRural	N/A	<u>European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference</u> (13.05.2025)
16	ScaleUp	N/A	Presentation of ROBIN toolbox during second session of ScaleUp training programme (01.10.2024) <u>European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference</u> (13.05.2025)
17	RuralBioUp	N/A	<u>European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference</u> (13.05.2025)
18	MainstreamBIO	N/A	<u>European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference</u> (13.05.2025)

Figure 36: ROBIN presentation during ScaleUP training (01 October 2024)

The list of relevant *projects* and *initiatives* was regularly updated on the ROBIN website. As of 25 August 2025, 17 projects were listed as related projects and 3 initiatives or networks (EuBioNet, CCRI and RBA) as related initiatives.

Figure 37: Screenshot of the ROBIN website where the related projects and initiatives are displayed

Dissemination networks

In addition to the direct collaboration with projects and initiatives, we also made use of ROBIN partners’ dissemination networks to increase the visibility and outreach of our activities. The table below provides an overview of the dissemination networks the consortium could draw upon.

Table 17: List of ROBIN’s dissemination networks

Multiplier for dissemination	Partner(s) that act as contact points
ERRIN Circular Bioeconomy working group	CAG, CTA
BIC bioeconomy platform	BIOPRO, CTA, RCM, CAG
Platform of Bioeconomy ERA NET Actions	RCM
S3P Traceability & Big Data	IFA, CTA, CAG
European Cluster Collaboration Platform	CTA
EITFood	CAG
European Committee of Regions	RCM, CAG, SRA, ZSK
SDSN Black Sea	AUTH
European Alliance for Innovation	PED
European Bioeconomy Alliance	RCM
COOPID Bioeconomy Clusters	MTU

European Bioeconomy Network	QPL, WR
Climate Pact Secretariat	PED

KPI results and conclusion

There are 2 project KPIs relating to synergies: KPI-3 (contributions to the CCRI) which was detailed in an earlier section and a KPI targeted synergies with initiatives & networks.

Table 18: Overview of synergies KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current Status (M34)	Details
Contributions to the CCRI	50	51	20 Governance Models 31 Good practices
Synergies with initiatives & networks	15	31	19 RBA + CCRI + EuBioNet + RIBES + BioGov.Net + BIOLOC + BIOREFINE Cluster Europe + Hubs4Circularity + NENUPHAR + SUSTRACK + SUSTCERT4BIOBASED + BIOTRANSFORM + DIVAGRI

Tables 17 and 18 show very clearly how ROBIN successfully cooperated with various projects and initiatives, going beyond the simple sharing of information on our respective websites and supporting the communication of upcoming events and dissemination of results. It pro-actively sought and implemented concrete collaboration in various formats. All partners were actively involved and contributed to the success of our synergetic activities.

6. Conclusions

A well-designed, clear, and robust dissemination and communication strategy was key for raising awareness of the ROBIN and its expected outcomes. This document outlined among others the communication tools and channels used for maximising ROBIN's visibility, presented the so-far progress of the project in terms of KPIs and provided thorough details in all aspects of ROBIN's communication and dissemination strategy.

The exceptional performance of ROBIN's KPIs and the engagement rates of users on our website and SMAs show the positive results of ROBIN's communication and dissemination strategy ensuring the project's maximum visibility. WR team has been closely monitoring the effectiveness of all partners dissemination efforts, continuously promoting ROBIN's presence internal and external events as well as engaging all interested stakeholders with information and activities related to ROBIN's toolbox.

This final version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results, delivered at the end of the project (M36), reflects the successful journey undertaken by all ROBIN partners in achieving, and in many cases exceeding, the KPIs of the project. It also highlights the continuous efforts made throughout the project to refine and enhance ROBIN's dissemination strategy, with the goal of improving visibility, increasing outreach, and ensuring greater impact across the target audiences.

Annexes

Annex I. Dissemination Reporting Template

Title	Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach
Acronym	ROBIN
Start	01/03/2022 (M1)
End	31/03/2025 (M36)
Notes:	Please fill out the form within 5 days for any dissemination and communication activity you carry out

The form below has been designed to help you keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activity you will carry out throughout the project. Dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, press releases, social media posts, website articles, interviews, events (conferences, Important: Specify the type of activity as well as the type of the audience(s) addressed using the categories provided in the drop-down menu. These are the categories used in the Participant Portal by the European Commission and it is important that we stick to them.

No. of Action	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity <i>(Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)</i>	Title of conference, workshop, publication, website article, etc.	Size of audience reached per type of stakeholder (in numbers)										Countries addressed <i>(use "global" if the action covers the whole world, use "EU-wide" if the action covers all EU Member States)</i>	Role and description of your organisation's involvement <i>(e.g. facilitator, interviewer, speaker, discussion leader)</i>	Type of project material used <i>(e.g. ROBIN leaflet, ROBIN poster, ROBIN presentation, etc.)</i>	Quantity of project material used <i>(no. of copies distributed per type of project material, use N/A if not applicable)</i>	Other ROBIN partners or external organisations responsible if involved <i>(use N/A if not applicable)</i>	Short description of the action	Other comments <i>(IF RELEVANT)</i>	Significant contacts made if and share data was given <i>(name, position, organisation, tel, e-mail)</i>	
					Scientific Community	Industry	Policy makers	Civil Society	General public	Media	Investors	Customers	Others	Total									
1	Example 10/13/2022	Virtual (zoom)	Participation in activities organized jointly with other Horizon Europe projects	<i>"Implementing circular systemic solutions in cities and regions"</i>	0	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	EU-wide	Speaker	N/A	N/A	N/A	Participation to a joint workshop with representatives of other Horizon Circular Cities projects. Round table for introducing ROBIN and receive information about the progress of other projects.	The participation in the event was successful since the project was introduced to important CS projects, opening new possibilities for synergies.	N/A

Annex II. Collaboration Agreement

Collaboration Agreement

Between

	<p><Insert logo of project/ initiative></p>
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This Collaboration Agreement is signed between:

1. **ROBIN “Deploying circular Bioeconomies at Regional level with a territorial approach” EU-funded project under grant agreement 101060504**, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by Ioanna Nydrioti (WR, WP leader)
2. **<Insert name of project/initiative>**, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by **<Insert name of the person who will sign this agreement on behalf of the project/ initiative>**

The Parties signing this Collaboration Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between the two projects/initiatives, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. This agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party.

Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:

WR on behalf of ROBIN agrees to the following:

- Display **<Insert project/ initiative>** link and logo on the ROBIN website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute **<Insert project/ initiative>** announcements (e.g. important events) on the ROBIN’s social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the ROBIN website to promote important **<Insert project/ initiative>** events.
- Publish **<Insert project/ initiative>** (guest) blog posts on the ROBIN’s blog.
- Invite **<Insert project/ initiative>** representatives to participate in events organised by ROBIN.
- Work with **<Insert project/ initiative>** to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders) together.
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of **<Insert project/ initiative>** on ROBIN social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.

- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of ROBIN and <Insert project/initiative> will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

<Insert name of organisation> on behalf of <Insert project/ initiative> agrees to the following:

- Display ROBIN link and logo on the <Insert project/ initiative> website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute ROBIN announcements (e.g. important events) on the <Insert project/ initiative> social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the <Insert project/ initiative> website to promote important ROBIN events.
- Publish ROBIN (guest) blog posts on the <Insert project/ initiative> blog.
- Invite ROBIN representatives to participate in events organised by <Insert project/ initiative>.
- Work with ROBIN to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders together).
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of ROBIN on <Insert project/ initiative> social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of <Insert project/ initiative> and ROBIN will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

Duration:

- Starting from <insert effective date> and ending on the <insert end date>.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate this Collaboration Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

ROBIN

Per:

Name:

Ioanna Nydrioti

Title:

Project Manager White Research

ROBIN's WP leader DEC

<Insert project/ initiative>

Per:

Name:

Title:

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

CONTACT US: info@robin-project.eu

VISIT: www.robin-project.eu

